

Non-linear evolution string vacuum

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In this paper, we consider the topological approach to evolution the universe.

We consider the geometry of the fields in the three-dimensional model Chern-Simons.

$$dS_{CS} = L_{CS} dx^3$$

Note that this model is similar to the topological geometry.

Thus, a mathematical description of the physical dynamics of the space in the form of a topological method is obtained.

If there is time, we use a 4-dimensional model for this universe in the form of Lagrangian the world.

$$dS = L dx^3 dt$$

For such the evolution the universe, can find a general action.

We formulate a hypothesis [1]. It is possible that there is a non-linear evolution for this topological geometry the space, then a 4-dimensional world and description of the evolution of the three-dimensional topology will be considered in the form of

$$L^2 > \beta \delta^3 L_{CS} / \delta t^3$$

In determining and normalizing the constant, the action has a physical meaning only for the parameters. We make certain steps, consider combinations of fundamental constants (speed light c , gravitational constant G , Planck constant h)

$$Gh/c^2 = 1/\beta = k$$

As can be seen, the evolution of the three-dimensional geometry occurs along the specified non-linear time and the inflation the 4-dimensional universe.

$$dS_0 = k L^2 dx^3 dt^3$$

However, the optimism is exist, perhaps this structure has a geometric formulation of the quantum field theory in form the string theory.

$$T^3 = k L^2$$

$$dS = T dx dt$$

It is interesting to note that this definition is almost equivalent to the equation for ordinary topological string.

In our non-linear field model, in this sense the string theory is a secondary concept.

It can be noted that the field space is proportional to the surface area. For instance information Φ for horizon the black hole

$$\Phi = F/4L^2$$

$$\Phi = \ln p$$

This indicates that the quantum field theory can be formulated by geometrical form, in particular on the world surface.

In this case, only a small part of this model was considered. In the next paper, we will make a deeper review and consequences for geometry, gravity, and even problem the time. In general, further research will show which geometric shape of the world will be expressed in the general model.